

Enhancing Public Health Data Understanding by Leveraging PCA for Aggregated Measure

Zhixin Lun¹

¹Department of Biostatistics and Informatics, Colorado School of Public Health, University of Colorado Anschutz Medical Campus, Aurora, CO 80045

Abstract

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) has been widely used for data reduction and clustering analysis. However, its interpretation strength has not been well applied to public health data. In matrix theory, the first principal component is the linear combination with maximum variance. The subsequent principal component is that with decreasing variance. It is straightforward to show this nature using matrix theory. However, when applied to public health data, the clinical meaning is not as easily understood as it is in mathematics.

We use the American Medical Association (AMA) End the Epidemic for naloxone and opioid prescriptions yearly aggregated time series measure to propose a pipeline for analyzing national public health using PCA. Our preliminary analysis shows that the first principal component might indicate a total national trend, which is roughly weighted sum contribution from all 50 states and Washington, D.C. We also leverage heatmaps to visualize how state-level changes in the first principal component (PC1) and discover interesting patterns, including some states leading the national trend. These findings might help audience understand the national public data from a different perspective. Therefore, the proposed pipeline can enhance our public health policy by minimizing geographic health disparities.

Key Words: PCA, correlation, heatmap, public health, opioid

1. Introduction

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a statistical technique widely used for dimensionality reduction and data analysis. It is particularly valued for its ability to reduce dimensionality and visualize data for clustering. PCA provides practical interpretations based on mathematical concepts, enriching insights and revealing the underlying structure of the data. Hotelling (1933) and Rao (1964) laid foundational work in multivariate statistical theory, offering both rigorous theoretical frameworks and insightful practical methodologies that continue to influence modern statistical analysis. Several classic textbooks on multivariate statistical analysis have played a pivotal role in reinforcing the practical utility of principal component analysis (PCA), notably Johnson and Wichern (2002) and Khatree and Naik (2000), which offer comprehensive treatments of both theory and application.

In this study, we aim to apply PCA in aggregated time series measures, which is one of the common data formats in public health research. Our goal is to address the following questions for non-statistician researchers and help them better understand the insights derived from PCA results.

- What is the nature of the principal components?
- How can loadings and scores be converted into more practical insights?

1.1 Data Structure

Aggregated time series data is a widely used and valuable resource in public health research. For example, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) publish COVID-19 surveillance data across all 50 states and the District of Columbia, while the American Medical Association (AMA) Advocacy Epidemic Report tracks opioid and naloxone prescriptions to monitor national trends. These datasets provide critical insights into both current conditions and long-term changes.

Figure 1 illustrates total opioid prescriptions in the U.S. from 2012 to 2023, with the final two columns showing percentage changes between 2022–2023 and 2012–2023, clearly indicating a downward trend. However, dense tabular visualizations often obscure deeper patterns, such as correlations across states or over time. Curious readers may also wonder how their own state compares to the national average—whether it is leading, lagging, or aligned. PCA offers a powerful approach to uncover and visualize these latent structures, making complex relationships more interpretable and accessible.

State	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	% change 2022-2023	% change 2012-2023
AK	538,444	527,424	504,837	472,242	449,773	396,863	341,605	289,506	281,934	273,228	248,125	228,758	-7.8%	-57.5%
AL	6,764,620	6,787,237	6,622,550	5,989,083	5,675,280	5,109,633	4,612,675	4,211,731	4,000,125	3,939,986	3,811,681	3,692,544	-3.2%	-45.4%
AR	3,489,534	3,472,929	3,563,197	3,351,237	3,279,101	3,038,955	2,688,861	2,505,785	2,351,007	2,345,070	2,253,147	2,232,913	-0.9%	-36.0%
AZ	5,641,320	5,383,787	5,382,585	5,153,251	4,877,335	4,299,031	3,629,048	3,331,763	3,079,860	2,995,602	2,810,665	2,670,937	-5.0%	-52.7%
CA	22,111,363	21,625,121	21,022,514	19,962,756	17,863,227	15,918,755	14,025,438	12,468,963	11,264,148	10,265,911	10,111,866	9,301,081	-8.0%	-58.3%
CO	4,154,847	4,056,826	3,995,835	3,768,991	3,475,641	3,063,076	2,650,143	2,394,096	2,254,731	2,155,634	2,057,631	1,961,134	-4.7%	-52.8%
CT	2,489,642	2,405,492	2,366,401	2,195,142	1,954,796	1,695,348	1,524,254	1,392,096	1,284,811	1,255,634	1,181,125	1,125,865	-4.8%	-54.8%
DC	409,905	399,384	399,384	325,525	325,525	291,288	297,288	214,824	182,214	172,287	155,529	136,240	-11.3%	-66.8%
DE	857,597	864,115	853,023	802,897	751,459	638,610	569,639	486,252	445,270	441,413	415,846	404,400	-2.8%	-52.9%
FL	15,956,382	15,656,348	15,285,437	14,445,377	14,494,935	13,492,693	11,765,998	10,757,508	10,204,581	10,037,758	9,508,116	9,031,687	-5.0%	-43.4%
GA	9,172,707	8,895,254	8,637,812	8,257,049	8,199,814	7,600,620	6,747,370	6,383,151	6,017,070	5,875,957	5,601,155	5,410,841	-3.4%	-41.0%
HI	628,606	610,397	708,162	715,203	674,071	600,712	524,122	459,732	413,086	376,320	354,159	324,555	-8.3%	-48.8%
IA	2,249,889	2,188,486	2,180,253	2,058,420	1,933,205	1,714,716	1,516,849	1,348,816	1,255,374	1,231,526	1,165,760	1,118,881	-4.0%	-50.3%
ID	1,569,901	1,544,048	1,528,318	1,449,967	1,380,824	1,269,143	1,138,421	1,084,069	1,003,773	988,024	947,561	933,451	-1.3%	-40.5%
IL	8,182,118	7,939,023	7,714,352	7,278,747	7,045,043	6,537,625	5,611,801	5,179,336	4,851,428	4,736,635	4,509,859	4,279,080	-5.0%	-47.7%
IN	7,211,749	6,929,043	6,337,467	5,895,913	5,599,591	5,014,997	4,381,891	4,041,888	3,805,516	3,713,253	3,570,512	3,380,108	-5.3%	-53.1%
KS	2,647,138	2,603,236	2,575,689	2,408,713	2,321,690	2,144,608	1,970,093	1,818,247	1,700,679	1,668,613	1,571,865	1,509,180	-4.0%	-43.0%
KY	5,029,827	4,819,225	4,713,085	4,333,328	4,146,136	3,765,938	3,483,663	3,262,156	3,103,589	2,999,976	2,835,127	2,701,880	-4.0%	-50.2%
LA	5,330,190	5,331,100	5,144,304	4,737,069	4,635,028	4,241,296	3,763,859	3,437,606	3,133,169	3,064,548	2,937,516	2,797,729	-4.8%	-47.5%
MA	4,408,497	4,278,827	4,110,150	3,767,881	3,344,073	2,870,931	2,552,926	2,338,657	2,184,410	2,166,881	2,039,790	1,940,609	-4.9%	-56.0%
MD	4,275,537	4,092,718	4,024,275	3,771,978	3,567,869	3,177,786	2,787,723	2,555,664	2,375,585	2,296,742	2,137,692	2,010,102	-6.0%	-53.0%
ME	1,228,983	1,177,849	1,128,264	1,043,601	915,998	762,975	664,422	613,897	558,528	541,363	499,756	468,769	-6.2%	-61.9%
MI	9,974,084	9,699,348	9,600,013	8,871,886	8,368,869	7,483,847	6,261,775	5,551,343	5,235,762	5,132,098	4,844,338	4,607,477	-4.9%	-53.3%
MN	3,253,343	3,141,236	3,070,660	2,858,458	2,548,820	2,203,447	1,933,544	1,736,329	1,639,362	1,599,644	1,491,333	1,412,669	-5.3%	-56.6%
MO	5,780,045	5,559,400	5,408,556	5,022,590	4,800,115	4,358,675	3,858,728	3,533,746	3,302,690	3,210,016	2,994,773	2,907,117	-3.2%	-49.8%
MS	3,428,837	3,372,978	3,271,685	3,099,012	2,964,104	2,626,963	2,172,703	1,932,909	1,829,754	1,844,854	1,804,435	1,789,508	-0.8%	-48.8%
MT	988,692	966,468	923,504	853,309	818,416	711,540	617,107	576,322	545,523	538,266	511,867	496,092	-3.1%	-50.3%
NC	10,669,466	9,936,055	9,631,211	9,040,085	8,522,875	7,524,407	6,484,050	6,096,562	5,743,531	5,588,519	5,283,628	5,122,822	-3.0%	-49.1%
ND	509,371	503,737	492,976	456,424	421,754	367,391	322,510	290,218	269,671	268,455	256,997	246,241	-4.2%	-51.7%
NE	1,404,035	1,392,799	1,366,565	1,265,325	1,226,643	1,109,786	1,008,494	916,465	869,094	846,776	805,543	786,818	-2.3%	-44.0%
NH	1,094,814	1,061,592	1,034,858	974,827	842,991	698,533	626,571	559,266	524,198	499,556	472,661	449,085	-5.0%	-59.0%
NJ	5,231,133	5,110,759	5,049,905	4,877,678	4,590,774	3,917,786	3,399,369	3,129,571	2,853,906	2,765,680	2,591,972	2,420,108	-6.6%	-53.7%
NM	1,578,948	1,463,637	1,452,681	1,411,310	1,323,711	1,157,563	1,010,859	927,309	852,748	809,844	762,291	717,226	-6.9%	-54.6%
NV	2,784,716	2,562,222	2,557,539	2,433,158	2,313,814	2,128,799	1,948,445	1,518,902	1,468,821	1,428,054	1,355,084	1,303,802	-3.8%	-53.2%
NY	10,027,002	9,879,293	9,352,222	9,064,011	8,565,080	7,637,406	6,754,370	6,171,717	5,620,038	5,481,821	5,144,471	4,855,817	-5.6%	-55.6%
OH	11,605,674	10,576,563	10,178,648	9,376,277	8,939,293	7,984,196	6,176,805	5,679,196	5,296,753	5,170,775	4,965,208	4,646,265	-4.5%	-60.0%
OK	4,899,817	4,685,528	4,245,635	4,001,964	3,805,798	3,453,173	3,136,607	2,625,191	2,387,240	2,373,881	2,295,387	2,218,116	-3.4%	-53.9%
OR	3,063,287	3,181,952	3,732,809	3,434,326	3,142,119	2,726,252	2,395,614	2,210,656	2,073,686	2,016,221	1,897,726	1,786,855	-5.8%	-54.9%
PA	10,940,840	10,264,417	10,016,259	9,459,767	8,733,513	7,366,164	6,347,857	5,680,043	5,175,725	5,009,651	4,716,850	4,496,339	-4.7%	-57.1%
RI	862,867	790,722	732,285	650,819	595,866	512,063	432,605	395,079	377,091	373,091	359,929	307,039	-33.8%	-64.4%
SC	4,082,056	4,058,301	4,072,172	4,571,844	4,343,882	3,951,185	3,444,824	3,146,548	2,953,777	2,884,106	2,744,960	2,633,030	-3.3%	-46.2%
SD	600,457	600,966	612,580	593,453	549,932	460,668	397,707	376,488	373,858	361,443	365,327	353,227	0.3%	-39.7%
TN	9,091,446	8,531,155	8,195,900	7,746,111	7,346,795	6,593,808	5,791,360	5,111,781	4,739,618	4,581,120	4,324,906	4,199,772	-2.9%	-53.8%
TX	20,221,249	19,567,992	19,013,036	16,881,775	16,423,406	15,056,529	13,776,467	12,976,738	11,802,255	11,183,326	10,668,420	10,279,153	-3.6%	-49.2%
UT	2,492,681	2,467,942	2,413,549	2,277,418	2,199,975	2,027,526	1,862,096	1,728,165	1,654,114	1,661,681	1,632,861	1,573,241	-3.6%	-36.9%
VA	6,729,624	6,355,576	6,116,477	6,163,611	5,257,250	4,438,279	3,797,462	3,488,748	3,219,217	3,133,795	2,959,895	2,838,817	-4.1%	-56.9%
VT	457,157	437,978	428,915	402,800	369,542	323,544	266,351	234,881	227,519	217,339	196,972	184,438	-6.4%	-58.7%
WA	5,539,742	5,368,583	5,344,529	5,064,846	4,744,600	4,255,414	3,735,652	3,329,414	3,116,684	3,063,191	2,876,180	2,771,230	-3.6%	-50.0%
WI	4,347,499	4,181,185	4,109,071	3,986,473	3,585,515	2,982,200	2,586,266	2,317,552	2,150,162	2,103,860	1,918,055	1,796,419	-6.4%	-58.7%
WV	2,484,010	2,305,181	2,231,907	1,940,145	1,658,291	1,382,077	1,165,134	1,024,107	931,415	909,384	833,378	783,254	-6.0%	-68.5%
WY	439,489	433,417	443,964	410,059	390,091	362,563	314,407	287,693	275,621	271,309	261,979	254,038	-3.0%	-41.0%
Total	369,657,377	351,766,372	344,476,595	323,806,981	291,590,568	192,688,222	168,859,967	153,956,683	143,377,621	139,614,372	131,896,599	125,930,878	-4.3%	-51.7%

Figure 1: Total opioid prescriptions in the US from 2012 to 2023. Source: AMA Advocacy Epidemic Report (https://end-overdose-epidemic.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/AMA-2024-Advocacy-Epidemic-report-opioid-prescriptions-IQVIA_FINAL.pdf).

1.2 Data Processing

The row-column relationship is a fundamental consideration for PCA practitioners. In statistical convention, rows typically represent subjects and columns represent variables. For the aggregated time series measures shown in Figure 1, each row corresponds to a state, and each column represents the yearly aggregated opioid prescription data.

A key step in data processing is to clearly define the research question, rather than assuming that public datasets are immediately ready for PCA. In this example, our goal is to uncover relationships between states—constructing principal components as combinations of states. For instance, PC1 can be expressed as:

$$PC_1 = a_{11}X_1 + a_{12}X_2 + \dots + a_{1p}X_p,$$

where X_i indicates the opioid prescription measure for i th state and coefficient a_{1i} represents the loading of the i th state in PC1 (we will explore loadings in more detail in the next section). This

formulation requires transposing the data frame so that states become variables and years are treated as observations.

Another important consideration is the effect of population size. It is reasonable to assume that higher opioid prescription counts may correlate with larger populations. To address this, we use percentage change calculations instead of raw counts, which helps mitigate population effects. For example, the percentage change in opioid prescriptions from 2012 to 2013 can be calculated as:

$$\text{Change Rate}_{2013} = \frac{\text{Precription}_{2013} - \text{Precription}_{2012}}{\text{Precription}_{2012}}$$

Similar calculations are applied across all years for each state.

Table 1: Processed data matrix after transposing and calculating year-over-year percentage changes in opioid prescriptions

	AK	AL	AR	AZ	CA	CO
2013	-0.0204	0.0004	-0.0004	-0.0456	-0.0307	-0.0211
2014	-0.0428	-0.0465	0.0259	-0.0002	-0.0278	-0.0174
2015	-0.0645	-0.0840	-0.0594	-0.0426	-0.0932	-0.0567

Table 1 shows a subset of the newly processed data matrix. The year 2012 is excluded because we do not have 2011 data to compute its change rate. This transformation offers several benefits:

1. **Population normalization:** The population effect is effectively canceled out if both the numerator and denominator are divided by each state's population.
2. **Trend clarity:** Similar to return rates in financial analysis, this approach reflects the true change trend regardless of the raw scale, making comparisons across states more meaningful.

In the next section, we will perform PCA using this processed data matrix and explore the interpretation of the resulting principal components.

2. Geospatial Interpretation of Principal Components

2.1 Loading and Correlation

The first principal component (PC1) is the eigenvector corresponding to the largest eigenvalue of the covariance matrix, as described in Section 1.2 and commonly found in classic textbooks. Each coefficient a_{1i} in the eigenvector is called a *loading*, which can be interpreted as the weight assigned to each state. Therefore, PC1 can be viewed as a weighted average of all state measures along the direction that maximizes the variance.

Although PCA is widely used in clustering analysis, clusters can often be identified by grouping points with similar values of PC1 and/or PC2. However, interpreting the loadings can be challenging, as they are unbounded $(-\infty, \infty)$ and lack a fixed scale, making direct comparison of their magnitudes less straightforward. As a result, their interpretation can be less intuitive for non-statisticians and practitioners.

To address this, we propose using the correlation between the original variables and the PC1 scores as an alternative measure of alignment. These correlation values, bounded within the interval $[-1, 1]$, offer a more interpretable and standardized metric for assessing how well each variable aligns with the principal component axes. This approach enhances accessibility and facilitates clearer communication of PCA results to broader audiences, including public health professionals and policymakers.

Interestingly, the correlation between raw data and PC1 scores are proportional to the loadings. This relationship can be illustrated using X_1 as an example, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Corr}(X_1, \mathbf{PC}_1) &= \frac{\text{Cov}(X_1, \mathbf{PC}_1)}{\sigma_{X_1}, \sigma_{\mathbf{PC}_1}} \\
&= \frac{a_{11}\text{Cov}(X_1, X_1) + a_{12}\text{Cov}(X_1, X_2) + \dots + a_{1n}\text{Cov}(X_1, X_n)}{\sigma_{X_1}\sqrt{\lambda_1}} \\
&= \frac{[\Sigma_X \mathbf{a}_1]_1}{\sigma_{X_1}\sqrt{\lambda_1}} \\
&= \frac{\lambda_1 a_{11}}{\sigma_{X_1}\sqrt{\lambda_1}} \\
&= \frac{\sqrt{\lambda_1} a_{11}}{\sigma_{X_1}}
\end{aligned}$$

where λ_1 is the eigenvalue corresponding to PC1. If the data matrix is standardized such that $\sigma_{X_1} = 1$, and we can conclude that the correlation between the raw variable and PC1 score is directly related to the corresponding loading value in PC1.

2.2 Principal Component Direction

An interesting exercise in Johnson & Wichern (2000) explores the application of PCA to stock market data, suggesting that PC1 may represent the overall market trend, while PC2 may capture sector-specific variations. Inspired by this, we interpret PC1 in our analysis as a representation of a national trend—capturing broad patterns shared across most states. In contrast, PC2 may reflect regional variations that deviate from the national pattern.

Additionally, the sign of the loadings is consistent with the sign of the correlations between the original variables and the principal component scores. This provides a practical and intuitive insight for public health data: the sign indicates whether a state’s trend is increasing or decreasing relative to the principal component direction.

3. Application

We use data from AMA 2024 Overdose Report IQVIA Data Opioid Prescribing and Data Naloxone to illustrate the application of PCA, focusing on the correlation between raw data and PC1 scores. The analysis was conducted in R (R Core Team, 2024) using the *prcomp()* function from *stats* package for PCA computation, and *plot_usmap()* from *usmap* package for heatmap generation.

Figure 2 displays two heatmaps: one for the original loadings and one for the correlations between raw data and PC1 scores. We observe that the patterns in both plots are nearly identical, differing only in scale—consistent with the mathematical relationship described in Section 2.1. However, the correlation scale offers clearer and more intuitive insights for readers.

We interpret PC1 as reflecting a national trend in opioid prescriptions. States shaded in dark blue are considered to be strongly aligned with this trend. In fact, the correlation values for all states range between -0.5 and -0.9 , indicating a moderate to strong association with the national pattern. Moreover, the negative sign of these correlations suggests a decreasing trend in opioid prescriptions, which aligns with national efforts to reduce opioid usage. These results reflect the impact of policy interventions and suggest promising progress in addressing the opioid epidemic.

Figure 2: Left: Heatmap for original PC1 loadings based on opioid prescription change rate data. Right: Heatmap of correlations between PC1 scores and raw opioid prescription change rate data.

We also applied the same pipeline to naloxone data. The AMA encourages physicians to prescribe naloxone to patients at risk of overdose, as well as to individuals who may be in a position to save a life. Therefore, we expect to observe an increasing trend in the correlation between naloxone change rate data and PC1 scores.

As shown in Figure 3, all correlations are positive, indicating a continued upward trend in naloxone prescriptions. States with lower correlation values may reflect regional patterns that diverge somewhat from the national trend, suggesting that local factors could be influencing prescribing behavior more strongly than national policy.

Figure 3: Heatmap of correlations between PC1 scores and raw naloxone prescription change rate data.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates how PCA can be effectively applied to aggregated public health time series data to uncover meaningful patterns and trends. We summarize the key takeaways as follows:

1. **Correlation as a proxy for loadings:** The correlation between raw variables and principal component (PC) scores is proportional to the loadings in the corresponding PC. This allows us to use correlation as a more interpretable measure of association between variables and the direction of the principal components.
2. **PC1 as a national trend indicator:** The first principal component (PC1) can be interpreted as capturing a national trend in state-level opioid and naloxone prescription data. Visualizing the correlation between raw variables and PC1 scores using heatmaps provides a fast and intuitive summary of how each state aligns with national patterns.

By transforming raw prescription data into percentage change rates and applying PCA, we offer a scalable and interpretable framework for analyzing complex public health datasets. This approach not only enhances understanding among non-statistical audiences but also supports data-driven decision-making for public health policy, particularly in identifying geographic disparities and monitoring the effectiveness of national interventions.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest related to this study.

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